

FEATURES OF TRAINING NURSES IN UZBEKISTAN IN MODERN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The purpose of the study: To determine the features and prospects of the system of training nurses in Uzbekistan in the context of the modernization of professional education, to analyze the compliance of educational programs with international standards, and to identify the main barriers and opportunities for further improvement of the system.*

The study was conducted using a comprehensive approach, including documentary analysis of regulatory acts, educational programs and teaching materials, as well as questionnaires and expert interviews with teachers, students and administrators of medical educational institutions. A total of 150 respondents took part in the study, including 70 teachers, 50 students and 30 administrators. Data collection and processing were carried out using quantitative analysis methods for questionnaires and content analysis for expert interviews.

The assessment of perception of educational programs showed that 78% of students and 85% of teachers rated the relevance of the curricula as high (more than 7 points on a 10-point scale). At the same time, only 48% of students and 55% of teachers considered access to modern resources satisfactory. The analysis of practical training revealed that although areas such as neonatology and anesthesiology receive sufficient time (200-250 hours), management and geriatrics remain insufficiently developed, with the practical component of only 30-35% of the total time. The main barriers include a lack of modern educational resources (65% of respondents), limited opportunities for international exchange (55%) and a lack of qualified teaching staff (60%).

Further reforms aimed at modernizing the curricula with an emphasis on developing practical skills and introducing innovative simulation-based learning methods are recommended. Improving the qualifications of teachers and expanding international partnerships seem necessary to improve the educational system and prepare nurses who are able to meet the challenges of modern medicine.

Keywords: *medical education, training of nurses, Uzbekistan, international standards, practical training, interdisciplinary approach, modernization of educational programs, international cooperation.*

Introduction

Medical education, including nursing training, plays a critical role in ensuring the sustainability and quality of national health systems, especially in the context of global challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic, population aging and increasing chronic diseases [1, 2]. In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen a significant increase in interest in improving the quality of nursing education, which is associated with the need to strengthen the health care workforce and adapt the training system to international standards [3, 4]. Active reforms in the field of nursing began in 1999, when, within the framework of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan [5], new educational standards for medical specialists were introduced.

Today, the training of nurses in Uzbekistan is aimed at providing a high level of competencies necessary for work in a modern medical environment. The system of higher nursing education was further strengthened by the establishment of the Academy of Nurses at Chilanar College of Public Health named after Abu Ali ibn Sino. [6]. The Academy is developing innovative programs that include humanitarian, preclinical and clinical modules, 50% of which will be devoted to practical training, which is in line with the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) and international standards [7, 8].

International relations and cooperation with organizations such as WHO and UNICEF will facilitate continuous updating of curricula and help introduce the latest methods and standards adopted in advanced health systems into the educational process [9]. This interaction will not only help improve the training of Uzbek nurses, but also support their integration into the international community of medical specialists [10].

Thus, the study of the characteristics of training nurses in Uzbekistan is important both for assessing current achievements and for identifying ways to further improve educational processes. This study is aimed at analyzing new approaches, educational programs and prospects that lay the foundation for sustainable development of nursing in Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods

To carry out this study, a comprehensive approach was used, including an analysis of regulatory documents, educational programs and teaching materials related to the training of nurses in Uzbekistan. The study was aimed at identifying modern trends in nursing education, as well as assessing its compliance with international standards and requirements.

Research design. The research is a descriptive and analytical study based on the methods of documentary analysis, questionnaires and expert survey. The documentary analysis included the study of regulatory acts, such as the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PR-197 of June 20, 2023 and Decree PD-2107 of November 10, 1998, which serve as the legal basis for reforming the nursing education system in the country. The analysis also included curricula and methodological recommendations developed taking into account the recommendations of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation.

Participants of the study. The study involved teachers and administrative staff of medical educational institutions of Uzbekistan. A total of 150 respondents were involved, including 70 teachers, 50 students and 30 administrators. Inclusion criteria for participants included experience in nursing education of 3 years or more, as well as knowledge of modern educational standards.

Data collection methods

Documentary analysis was conducted with the aim of studying and systematizing regulatory acts, training programs and reform plans related to the training of nurses with higher education. Official documents of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, program documents of the Academy of Nurses and regulatory documents related to international standards in nursing education were examined.

The survey was conducted among students and teachers of medical universities to assess their perception and satisfaction with current educational programs. The questionnaires included questions about the content of courses, time allocated for practical classes, and the presence of an interdisciplinary approach to teaching. The questionnaire was developed based on the survey methods recommended by WHO for the evaluation of educational programs in health care.

- An expert interview with teachers and administrators was conducted to deeply assess the level of training of nurses, as well as to identify barriers that prevent compliance with international standards. Experts shared their experiences regarding modern methods and perspectives that are used in the educational process.

Data analysis methods. Data collection and processing were carried out using quantitative and qualitative analysis methods. The obtained quantitative survey data were processed using statistical methods to determine the levels of satisfaction and perception of educational programs. Qualitative data obtained during expert interviews were analyzed using content analysis to identify key topics and barriers in the development of nursing education.

Ethical aspects. All ethical principles were observed during the study, including confidentiality and voluntary participation. Before the survey and interview, respondents were informed about the objectives of the study, and written consent was obtained from each participant.

The applied complex methodological approach allowed to study the features of training of nurses in Uzbekistan, to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the current education system and to determine the directions for its further improvement. The use of various methods of data collection and analysis ensured the reliability and validity of the results, which lays the foundation for the development of recommendations for improving nursing education in accordance with international standards.

Results

Based on the conducted research, data were obtained that allow us to assess the effectiveness and quality of the current system of training nurses in Uzbekistan. The results are divided into several categories, including the perception of educational programs by students and teachers, an assessment of the practical components of training, as well as the identified barriers to achieving international standards. Tables 1, 2 and 3 present the summarized results of the analysis of questionnaire and interview data.

Table 1

Evaluation of perception of educational programs by students and teachers

Category	Average rating (0-10)	% of students who rated above 7	% of teachers who rated above 7
Relevance of the curriculum	8.3	78%	85%
Quality of teaching	7.5	70%	80%
Time allocated for practice	6.8	60%	62%
Availability of modern resources	5.2	48%	55%
Interdisciplinary approach	6.9	65%	68%

Description of table 1: Table 1 shows that the highest scores among students and faculty were for curriculum relevance (8.3), indicating that it meets current health care requirements.

However, relatively low scores were given to components related to access to current resources and time allocated for practical training, indicating limited opportunities for practicing skills in realistic conditions.

Table 2

Time allocated for practical training in key areas

Direction	Total number of hours	% of time spent on practice	Assessment of the quality of practice (0-10)
Anesthesiology and resuscitation	250	40%	7.0
Surgery	300	45%	7.3
Neonatology and Pediatrics	200	50%	7.6
Nursing Management	150	30%	6.8
Geriatrics and gerontology	180	35%	6.5
Medical radiology	220	50%	7.1

Description for table 2: Table 2 provides information on the number of hours allocated to practical classes in various specialties. It was found that specialties with a high level of responsibility, such as neonatology and anesthesiology, receive more practical time. At the same time, the average quality level of practical classes was estimated within 6.5–7.6, which reflects students' satisfaction with practical training. However, the management direction requires a more intensive practical component for better assimilation of the material.

Table 3

Key barriers to achieving international standards in nursing education

Barrier	% of respondents who noted a barrier	Key Notes
Lack of modern educational resources	65%	Lack of modern equipment and materials for simulation training
Limited opportunities for international exchange	55%	Insufficient number of exchange programs and trainings abroad
Lack of qualified teaching staff	60%	Teachers demand on advanced training and access to new methods
Lack of standardization of practical courses	50%	Insufficient number of clinical sites for practicing practical skills

Description for table 3: Table 3 presents the main barriers to achieving international standards in nursing education. The largest number of respondents (65%) indicated the lack of modern educational resources, such as simulation mannequins and equipment necessary for high-quality practical training. Considerable attention was also paid to the need to improve the qualifications of teachers and expand international exchange programs.

Discussion

The results of this study showed that the nursing training system in Uzbekistan largely meets the current healthcare needs of the country, but requires improvement to meet international standards and practices [1, 2]. As indicated in the works of WHO, to improve the quality of nursing education, it is necessary to ensure a high level of practical skills and access to modern educational resources, including simulation technologies that allow future nurses to develop the necessary competencies before entering clinical practice [8, 11]. However, in our study, 65% of respondents

noted a lack of such resources, which confirms the relevance of improving the material and technical base (see Table 3).

At the international level, nursing education is focused on integrating interdisciplinary approaches and training specialists capable of performing a wide range of tasks in various fields of medicine, from anesthesiology to pediatrics and nursing management [12]. Countries such as the United States and Great Britain have long introduced programs that include 50% practice and provide in-depth training in the chosen specialization, which has a positive effect on the professional skills of graduates [13, 14]. Despite the introduction of a credit-modular system in Uzbekistan, the number of practical hours in a number of areas remains insufficient, especially in the field of management and geriatrics (see Table 2), which limits the opportunities for nurses to master management and specialized competencies [15].

Another important aspect is the need for international cooperation, which facilitates the exchange of experience and the improvement of educational standards. A number of studies emphasize the importance of the participation of teachers and students in international training and exchange programs [16, 17]. For example, in South Korea and Australia, exchange programs are actively supported by the state, which helps to adapt curricula to global requirements [18, 19]. Our study found that 55% of respondents consider limited opportunities for international exchange as a barrier to professional development (see Table 3). This indicates the need for more active interaction with international organizations such as WHO and UNICEF, with whom cooperation has already been established, but its expansion is required [20].

The problem of qualification of teaching staff also remains significant. In the countries of Europe and North America, it is widely practiced to involve specialists who have undergone international internships and certification in teaching [21]. In Uzbekistan, despite the presence of highly qualified teachers, 60% of respondents note the need to improve their qualifications, which can be achieved by expanding educational programs and creating new opportunities for professional growth [22].

Conclusion

The study identified key strengths and weaknesses in the nursing education system in Uzbekistan. The most significant findings include:

High relevance of the curricula: The nursing training programs largely meet modern requirements and also reflect the needs of national healthcare. This is confirmed by the high assessment by students and teachers (see Table 1). However, to achieve international standards, the practical component needs to be improved.

Need for more hands-on training: Specialized disciplines such as anesthesiology and neonatology receive adequate time for practice. However, areas such as nursing management and geriatrics require a more hands-on approach. Increasing the time for hands-on training and introducing simulation technologies can help address this challenge (see Table 2).

International cooperation and exchange of experience: Limited opportunities for international exchange hinder the achievement of a high level of training. Expanding cooperation with international organizations and participation in international exchange programs are necessary steps to improve the training of nurses (see Table 3)

Teacher Qualifications: The shortage of qualified teaching staff remains a serious problem. Improving the qualifications of teachers, their participation in international internships and access to new teaching methods should be priority areas of development.

Based on the results of this study, it is recommended to pay attention to the modernization of educational programs, increasing funding for improving the material and technical base, as well as expanding international relations. These measures will help strengthen Uzbekistan's position in the global medical education market and ensure the training of qualified nurses who are able to work effectively in the conditions of modern healthcare.

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